

 μ_I g -Dense sets and μ_I g - Baire spaces in GITSG.Helen Rajapushpan^{1*}, P. Sivagami² and G. Hari Siva Annam³¹Research scholar, Reg.No:19212102092014,PG and Research Department of Mathematics, Kamaraj college,
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Abstract: Our aim is to bring the idea of μ_I g -DGITS, μ_I g -NDGITS, μ_I g -CDGITS and μ_I g -Baire space on μ_I g -closed sets in GITS and some of the basic properties are to be discussed.

Key words: μ_I g -DGITS, μ_I g -NDGITS, μ_I g -rare set, μ_I g -CDGITS, μ_I g -SDGITS, μ_I g -FCGITS, μ_I g -SCGITS, μ_I g -Baire space, $D^*(\mu_I)$, $Nd^*(\mu_I)$, $Cd^*(\mu_I)$, $Sd^*(\mu_I)$ and $\mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$.

1. Introduction

In 1996, the idea of an intuitionistic set was first initiated by Dogen Coker. It is the specialization of an intuitionistic fuzzy set (IFS). He also investigated some of their characterizations. After that in 2020, G.Helen Rajapushpan et al [10] were spend a lot of time to basic concepts of an intuitionistic topology and a generalized topology. Finally they covered the inspiring growth of μ_I g -closed sets in GITS and discussed their basic behaviours. In 2021, they initiated and explained some of their new operators named as μ_I g -border, μ_I g -Exterior and μ_I g -Frontier. At first, the fuzzy nowhere dense set was initiated by R.Dhavaseelan [4]. Later he developed intuitionistic fuzzy Baire spaces. In this paper, we concerning some results of μ_I g -dense, μ_I g -nowhere dense and μ_I g -Baire spaces. Also we elaborate it with several related counter examples.

2. Primary Needs

Here we give some notions and results on GITS. On the whole paper, we mentioned GITS (X, μ_I) as X (Non-void set). An intuitionistic subset (ISs) $A \subseteq X$ is of the form $A = \langle X, A_i, A_j \rangle$, where A_i and A_j are respectively called as member and non-members of A which satisfying the condition $A_i \cap A_j = \phi$. The pair (X, τ) is said to be an intuitionistic topological space (ITS) if (i) $\phi \sim, X \sim, \cup_{k=1}^n A_k$ and $\cap_{k=1}^n A_k$ are in τ . Here members of τ is known as an intuitionistic open set (IOS) in X and the complement of IOS is called an intuitionistic closed set (ICS). Let μ_I be the collection of ISs of X . Then X is said to be GITS if $\phi \sim \in \mu_I$ and μ_I is closed under arbitrary unions. Then the elements of μ_I is called μ_I -open and their complements are named as μ_I -closed sets. $c_{\mu_I}(A)$ is defined as the intersection of all μ_I -closed sets containing A and $i_{\mu_I}(A)$ is defined as the union of all μ_I -open set contained in A . If $c_{\mu_I}(A) \subseteq U$

whenever $A \subseteq U$ where U is μ_I -open set in X then $A \subseteq X$ is called $\mu_I g$ -closed set. Every μ_I -closed set is a $\mu_I g$ -closed set. $c_{\mu_I}^*(A)$ and $i_{\mu_I}^*(A)$ are defined as follows, $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \bigcap \{F : F \text{ is } \mu_I g\text{-closed set and } A \subseteq F\}$ and $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \bigcup \{G : G \text{ is } \mu_I g\text{-open set, } G \subseteq A\}$. If A is $\mu_I g$ -closed (resp. $\mu_I g$ -open) then $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = A$ (resp. $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = A$). The $\mu_I g$ -Exterior and $\mu_I g$ -border[13] are described as $E_{\mu_I}^*(A) = i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})$ and $b_{\mu_I}^*(A) = A - i_{\mu_I}^*(A)$. Also $\mu_I g$ -Frontier is stated that the difference between $\mu_I g$ -closure and $\mu_I g$ -interior (in short $Fr_{\mu_I}^*$). $c_{\mu_I}(A) = X_{\sim}$ (resp. $c_{\mu_I}(\bar{A}) = X_{\sim}$) is named as an μ_I -dense (resp. μ_I -condense). Also a subset A of an ITS of X is said to be μ_I -nowhere dense if the μ_I -closure of A contains no μ_I -interior points or $i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A)) = \phi_{\sim}$. Every subset of a μ_I -nowhere dense set is a μ_I -nowhere dense set. We construct an important result that the relation between $c_{\mu_I}^*(A)$ and $i_{\mu_I}^*(A)$ using complements are as follows (a) $c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(A)}$; (b) $\overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(A)} = i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})$; (c) $\overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})} = i_{\mu_I}^*(A)$; (d) $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})}$.

3. $\mu_I g$ -Dense, $\mu_I g$ -Nowhere Dense, $\mu_I g$ -Codense & $\mu_I g$ -Somewhere Dense sets in GITS

In this section, we introduce the different concepts in GITS such as $\mu_I g$ -DGITS, $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS, $\mu_I g$ -CDGITS and $\mu_I g$ -SDGITS and discuss their properties. Also we examine the relations among them and establish the peculiar qualities along with $E_{\mu_I}^*, b_{\mu_I}^*$ and $Fr_{\mu_I}^*$. More awesome illustrations are given. We call $\langle X, \phi, X \rangle$ as \mathcal{E} , $\langle X, \phi, \phi \rangle$ as \mathcal{O} and $\langle X, X, \phi \rangle$ as \mathcal{U} .

Definition 3.1. An ISS A in X is said to be $\mu_I g$ -Dense in GITS ($\mu_I g$ -DGITS) if $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{U}$. Throughout this paper $D^*(\mu_I)$ denotes the set of all $\mu_I g$ -DGITS.

Definition 3.2. If $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) = \mathcal{E}$ then we call it as $\mu_I g$ -Nowhere Dense in GITS ($\mu_I g$ -NDGITS). Here after $Nd^*(\mu_I)$ denotes the set of all $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS.

Definition 3.3. An ISS A in X is said to be $\mu_I g$ -Co Dense in GITS ($\mu_I g$ -CDGITS) if $c_{\mu_I}^*\bar{A} = \mathcal{U}$. The collection of $\mu_I g$ -CDGITS is stand as a symbol for $Cd^*(\mu_I)$.

Example 3.1. Let $X = \{1_X, 2_X, 3_X\}$ with $\mu_I = \{\mathcal{E}, \langle X, \{2_X\}, \{1_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{2_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{2_X, 3_X\}, \{1_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{3_X\}, \{1_X, 2_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{2_X\}, \{3_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{3_X, 2_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \phi, \{3_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{3_X\}, \phi \rangle\}$. Then $D^*(\mu_I) = \{\mathcal{U}, \langle X, \{2_X, 3_X\}, \{1_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{2_X, 3_X\}, \phi \rangle\}$, $Nd^*(\mu_I) = \{\mathcal{E}, \langle X, \{1_X\}, \{2_X, 3_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \phi, \{2_X, 3_X\} \rangle\}$ and $Cd^*(\mu_I) = \{\langle X, \phi, \{2_X, 3_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{1_X\}, \{2_X, 3_X\} \rangle, \mathcal{E}\}$.

Remark 3.1. The complement of $\mu_I g$ -DGITS need not be a $\mu_I g$ -DGITS. We explained with an example. Now consider the topological space $X = \{u', v', w'\}$ with $\mu_I = \{\mathcal{E}, \langle X, \phi, \{v'\} \rangle, \langle X, \{u'\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{u', v'\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{u'\}, \{w'\} \rangle\}$. Then $D^*(\mu_I) = \{\langle X, \{u', v'\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{u', w'\}, \{v'\} \rangle, \mathcal{U}\}$ and the complement of $D^*(\mu_I)$ is $\{\langle X, \phi, \{u', v'\} \rangle, \langle X, \{w'\}, \{u', v'\} \rangle, \mathcal{E}\}$ which is not a $\mu_I g$ -DGITS.

Proposition 3.1. Every $\mu_I g$ -DGITS is a μ_I -dense but the converse is not true.

Proof. Clearly $c_{\mu_I}(A) \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Suppose A is a $\mu_I g$ -DGITS then $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{U}$. Now

$\mathcal{U} = c_{\mu_I}^* (A) \subseteq c_{\mu_I} (A)$. Therefore A is a μ_I -DGITS. But the converse is not valid. Now we express with the help of counter example. \square

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{i_X, j_X, k_X\}$ with $\mu_I = \{ \mathcal{E}, \langle X, \{i_X\}, \{j_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{j_X\}, \{k_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{i_X, j_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{i_X\}, \phi \rangle \}$. Then $\mathcal{O}, \langle X, \phi, \{k_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{i_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{i_X\}, \{j_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{i_X\}, \{k_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{i_X\}, \{j_X, k_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{j_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{j_X\}, \{k_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{k_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{k_X\}, \{i_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{j_X, k_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{j_X, k_X\}, \{i_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{k_X, i_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{k_X, i_X\}, \{j_X\} \rangle$ are all μ_I -dense at the same time they are not μ_I g -DGITS.

Proposition 3.2. If $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and $B \subseteq X$, the following properties holds.

- (i) $X_{\sim} \in D^*(\mu_I)$.
- (ii) $\phi_{\sim} \in D^*(\mu_I)$.
- (iii) $A \cup B \in D^*(\mu_I)$.
- (iv) $c_{\mu_I}^* (A)$ is also a μ_I g -DGITS.
- (v) Every superset of a μ_I g -DGITS is a μ_I g -DGITS.

Proposition 3.3. Let A be an ISs of X . If $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$ then for any non-empty μ_I g -closed subset F such that $A \subseteq F$, we have $F = \mathcal{U}$.

Proof. Assume $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and F is a μ_I g -closed subset of a X such that $A \subseteq F$. Since $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$, $c_{\mu_I}^* (A) = \mathcal{U}$. By assumption, F is μ_I g -closed and $A \subseteq F$, it follows that, $\mathcal{U} = c_{\mu_I}^* (A) \subseteq c_{\mu_I}^* (F) = F$. Therefore $F = \mathcal{U}$. \square

Proposition 3.4. Let $T \subseteq X$. If $T \in D^*(\mu_I)$ then $S \cap T \neq \mathcal{E}$ for any non-void μ_I g -open subset S of X .

Proof. Assume that $T \in D^*(\mu_I)$. Then for any non-void μ_I g -closed subset F such that $T \subseteq F$, we have $F = \mathcal{U}$. Suppose $S \cap T \neq \mathcal{E}$ for some non-void μ_I g -open subset S of X then $T \subseteq X - S$. Since S is μ_I g -open in X , $X - S$ is μ_I g -closed in X . By our assumption, $X - S = \mathcal{U}$. Therefore $S = \mathcal{E}$ which is a contradiction to S is a non-void μ_I g -open subset of X . \square

Proposition 3.5. Let $T \subseteq X$. If $T \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and μ_I g -open set then $S \subseteq c_{\mu_I}^* (T \cap S)$.

Proof. Suppose $s \in S$ but $s \notin c_{\mu_I}^* (T \cap S)$ then $s \in \overline{c_{\mu_I}^* (T \cap S)} \Rightarrow s \in i_{\mu_I}^* (\overline{c_{\mu_I}^* (T \cap S)}) \subseteq \overline{T} \cup \overline{S}$ and so $s \in \overline{T}$ or $s \in \overline{S}$.

Case: (i) Suppose $s \in \overline{T}$, then $S \subseteq \overline{T}$. This implies $S \cap T = \mathcal{E}$ which is a contradiction to proposition :3.4. Therefore $s \in c_{\mu_I}^* (T \cap S)$.

Case: (ii) Suppose $s \in \overline{S}$, then $S \subseteq \overline{S}$. It tends to a contradiction. Hence we have $s \in c_{\mu_I}^* (T \cap S)$.

In both the cases we get $S \subseteq c_{\mu_I}^* (T \cap S)$. \square

Corollary 3.1. Let $T \subseteq X$. If $T \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and S is a μ_I g -open set then $S \subseteq c_{\mu_I}^* (T \cap S) \subseteq c_{\mu_I} (T \cap S)$.

Proposition 3.6. Let $A \subseteq X$. If $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and S is a μ_I g -open in X then $Fr_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \bar{A}$.

Proof. Assume that $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and μ_I g -open in X . Then $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{U}$ and $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = A$. Now $Fr_{\mu_I}^*(A) = c_{\mu_I}^*(A) - i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \bar{A}$. \square

Proposition 3.7. If $A \subseteq X$ is a μ_I g -DGITS then $Fr_{\mu_I}^*(A) = c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})$.

Proof. Now $Fr_{\mu_I}^*(A) = c_{\mu_I}^*(A) - i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})$. \square

Remark 3.2. The reverse of proposition:3.7 is not stand.

Example 3.3. Let $X = \{a_X, b_X, c_X\}$ with $\mu_I = \{ \mathcal{E}, \langle X, \{a_X, c_X\}, \{b_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{c_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{a_X, c_X\}, \phi \rangle \}$ Then $D^*(\mu_I) = \{ \langle X, \{a_X, c_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{a_X, c_X\}, \{b_X\} \rangle, \mathcal{U} \}$. Take $A = \langle X, \phi, \{b_X\} \rangle$. Then $c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}) = \langle X, \{b_X\}, \phi \rangle$ and $Fr_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \langle X, \{b_X\}, \phi \rangle$. Therefore $Fr_{\mu_I}^*(A) = c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})$ but $A = \langle X, \phi, \{b_X\} \rangle$ is not a μ_I g -DGITS.

Proposition 3.8. An ISs A is μ_I g -DGITS iff $E_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$.

Proof. Suppose A is a μ_I g -DGITS, then $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{U}$. Now $E_{\mu_I}^*(A) = i_{\mu_I}^*\bar{A} = \overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(A)} = \mathcal{E}$. Conversely, assume that $E_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$. Then $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})} = \mathcal{U}$. \square

Remark 3.3. The complement of μ_I g -NDGITS need not be a μ_I g -NDGITS. In example:3.3, $Nd^*(\mu_I) = \{ \langle X, \phi, \{a_X, b_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{c_X\}, \{a_X, b_X\} \rangle, \mathcal{E} \}$. The complement of μ_I g -NDGITS is $\{ \langle X, \{a_X, b_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{a_X, b_X\}, \{c_X\} \rangle, \mathcal{U} \}$ which is not a μ_I g -NDGITS.

Proposition 3.9. Every μ_I g -NDGITS is a μ_I -nowhere dense set but the converse is not true.

Proof. Suppose A is a μ_I g -NDGITS then $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) = \mathcal{E}$. Now $i_{\mu_I}(c_{\mu_I}(A)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) = \mathcal{E}$ and hence A is a μ_I -Nowhere Dense set. But the converse is not true. Now we can see the following illustration. Let $X = \{i_X, j_X, k_X\}$ with $\mu_I = \{ \mathcal{E}, \langle X, \{i_X\}, \{j_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{j_X\}, \{k_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{i_X, j_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{i_X\}, \phi \rangle \}$. Then $\langle X, \phi, \{j_X, k_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{j_X\}, \{i_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \phi, \{i_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \phi, \{j_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \phi, \{k_X, i_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{j_X\}, \{i_X, k_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{k_X\}, \{j_X\} \rangle$ are all μ_I -nowhere dense set at the same time they are not μ_I g -NDGITS. \square

Proposition 3.10. Let A be an ISs of X . If $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ in X , then $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$.

Proof. By using the definition of μ_I g -NDGITS and the result $A \subseteq c_{\mu_I}^*(A)$, we get $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$. The converse of above proposition may not stand. \square

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{p_X, q_X\}$ with $\mu_I = \{ \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{O}, \langle X, \{p_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \phi, \{p_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{p_X\}, \{q_X\} \rangle \}$ and μ_I g -closed set = $\{ \mathcal{U}, \langle X, \phi, \{p_X\} \rangle, \mathcal{O}, \langle X, \{q_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{p_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{q_X\}, \{p_X\} \rangle \}$. Take $A = \mathcal{E}$ and $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$. Then $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) = \langle X, \phi, \{p_X\} \rangle \neq \mathcal{E}$. Therefore A is not a μ_I g -NDGITS. But the converse is true only if A is a μ_I g -closed set. The following corollary gives the crystal clear idea about it.

Corollary 3.2. Let $A \subseteq X$. If A is μ_I g -closed set with $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$ then A is μ_I g -NDGITS.

Proof. Suppose A is a μ_I g -closed set in X with $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$ then $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) = i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$. Therefore A is a μ_I g -NDGITS. \square

Example 3.5. Consider the topological space $X = \{f_X, g_X, h_X\}$ with $\mu_I = \{\mathcal{E}, \langle X, \{f_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \phi, \{g_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{h_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{f_X, h_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{f_X\}, \{g_X, h_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{f_X\}, \{g_X\} \rangle\}$ and μ_I g -closed set $= \{\mathcal{U}, \langle X, \phi, \{f_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \phi, \{h_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \phi, \{h_X, f_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{g_X\}, \{f_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{g_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{g_X\}, \{h_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{f_X, g_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{g_X\}, \{f_X, h_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{f_X, g_X\}, \{h_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{g_X, h_X\}, \phi \rangle, \langle X, \{g_X, h_X\}, \{f_X\} \rangle\}$. Here we take a μ_I g -closed set A is $\langle X, \phi, \{h_X, f_X\} \rangle$ with $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$. Then $Nd^*(\mu_I) = \{\langle X, \phi, \{h_X, f_X\} \rangle, \langle X, \{g_X\}, \{f_X, h_X\} \rangle, \mathcal{E}\}$. Therefore A is a μ_I g -NDGITS.

Note 3.1. An ISSs A of X is said to be a μ_I g -rare set if $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$.

Proposition 3.11. Let $A \subseteq X$. If $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and a μ_I g -open set then $\bar{A} \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$.

Proof. Suppose A is a μ_I g -DGITS and μ_I g -open set in X . Now $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})) = i_{\mu_I}^*(\overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(A)}) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(A)} = \mathcal{E}$. Therefore \bar{A} is a μ_I g -NDGITS. \square

Proposition 3.12. Let $A \subseteq X$. If $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and a μ_I g -open set in X such that $B \subseteq \bar{A}$ then $B \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$.

Proof. From proposition:3.11, $\bar{A} \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$. Since $B \subseteq \bar{A}$, $c_{\mu_I}^*(B) \subseteq c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})$. Now $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(B)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})) = \mathcal{E}$. Hence B is a μ_I g -NDGITS. \square

Proposition 3.13. Let $A \subseteq X$. If $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ then

- (i) $\bar{A} \in D^*(\mu_I)$.
- (ii) $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$.
- (iii) $\overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(A)} \in D^*(\mu_I)$.

Proof. (i) Suppose $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ then by proposition:3.4, we get $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$. Now $c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(A)} = \mathcal{U}$. Therefore \bar{A} is a μ_I g -DGITS.

(ii) Suppose $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ then $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) = \mathcal{E}$. Now $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A))) = i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) = \mathcal{E}$. Therefore $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$.

(iii) Now $c_{\mu_I}^*(\overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(A)}) \subseteq c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(A)} = \mathcal{U}$. Then $\overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(A)} \in D^*(\mu_I)$. \square

Proposition 3.14. Let $A, B \subseteq X$. If $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and $B \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ then $A \cap B \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$.

Proof. Assume that $A \in D^*(\mu_I)$ and $B \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$. Now $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A \cap B)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A) \cap c_{\mu_I}^*(B)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) \cap i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(B)) = i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) \cap \mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}$. Hence $A \cap B \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$. \square

Proposition 3.15. *Let A be an ISs of X . Then the following are true.*

- (i) *If $B \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ and $A \subseteq B$ then $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$. (ie) Every subset of a μ_I g -NDGITS is μ_I g -NDGITS.*
- (ii) *If $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ or $B \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ then $A \cap B \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$.*
- (iii) *If $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ then $b_{\mu_I}^*(A) = A$.*

Proof. (i) Now $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(B)) = \mathcal{E}$. Therefore $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$.

(ii) $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A \cap B)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A) \cap c_{\mu_I}^*(B)) \subseteq i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) \cap i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(B)) = \mathcal{E}$.
Therefore $A \cap B \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$.

(iii) Obvious. The reverse of (iii) is not valid. Now we explain with an example. In example:3.5, $b_{\mu_I}^*(\mathcal{O}) = \mathcal{O}$ but \mathcal{O} is not a μ_I g -NDGITS.

The idempotency property of μ_I g -border is fails in GITS but it is valid only if an ISs is μ_I g -NDGITS. □

Proposition 3.16. *Let $A \subseteq X$. Then $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$ iff $c_{\mu_I}^*(i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})) = \mathcal{U}$.*

Proof. Necessary Part: Suppose $A \in Nd^*(\mu_I)$, $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) = \mathcal{E}$. Now $c_{\mu_I}^*(i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})) = c_{\mu_I}^*(\overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(A)}) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A))} = \mathcal{U}$.

Sufficient Part: Suppose $c_{\mu_I}^*(i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A})) = \mathcal{U}$. Now $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) = \overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(\overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(A)})} = \overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}))} = \mathcal{E}$. □

Remark 3.4. *The complement of μ_I g -CDGITS need not be a μ_I g -CDGITS. Now we explain with an example. Consider the topological space $X = \{l_X, m_X, n_X\}$ with $\mu_I = \{\mathcal{E}, < X, \{l_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{l_X\}, \{m_X\} >, < X, \{m_X\}, \{n_X\} >, < X, \{m_X, l_X\}, \phi >\}$ and Then $Cd^*(\mu_I) = \{< X, \phi, \{l_X, m_X\} >, < X, \{n_X\}, \{l_X, m_X\} >, \mathcal{E}\}$. Then the complement of $Cd^*(\mu_I)$ is $\{< X, \{l_X, m_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{l_X, m_X\}, \{n_X\} >, \mathcal{U}\}$ which is not a $Cd^*(\mu_I)$.*

Proposition 3.17. *Every μ_I g -CDGITS is a μ_I -codense set but the converse is not true.*

Proof. Clearly $c_{\mu_I}(\bar{A}) \subseteq \mathcal{U}$. Suppose A is a μ_I g -CDGITS then $c_{\mu_I}(\bar{A}) = \mathcal{U}$. Now $\mathcal{U} = c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}) \subseteq c_{\mu_I}(\bar{A})$. Therefore A is a μ_I -codense set. But the converse is not valid. Now we expressed with the help of a counter example. □

Example 3.6. *In example:3.2, the upcoming sets are μ_I -codense but not μ_I g -CDGITS. $< X, \phi, \{j_X, k_X\} >, \mathcal{O}, < X, \phi, \{i_X\} >, < X, \phi, \{j_X\} >, < X, \phi, \{k_X\} >, < X, \{k_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{k_X\}, \{i_X\} >, < X, \{k_X\}, \{j_X\} >, < X, \{j_X, k_X\}, \{i_X\} >, < X, \phi, \{k_X, i_X\} >, < X, \{i_X\}, \{j_X, k_X\} >, < X, \{j_X\}, \{k_X\} >, < X, \{j_X\}, \{i_X, k_X\} >.$*

Proposition 3.18. *Every μ_I g -NDGITS is a μ_I g -CDGITS.*

Proof. Using Proposition:3.10 and the definition of μ_I g -CDGITS, we get a result. □

Remark 3.5. *The converse is not valid Now we explain with a clear example.*

Example 3.7. Consider the topological space $X = \{ a_X, b_X, c_X \}$ with $\mu_I = \{ \mathcal{E}, < X, \{ c_X \}, \{ a_X \} >, < X, \{ b_X \}, \{ a_X, c_X \} >, < X, \{ b_X, c_X \}, \{ a_X \} > \}$. Then $Cd^*(\mu_I) = \mathcal{E}$. But in this topology, μ_I g -NDGITS does not exist.

Proposition 3.19. Let A be an ISs of X . Then $A \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$ iff A is μ_I g -rare set (or) $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$.

Proof. Suppose $A \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$ then $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \overline{c_{\mu_I}^*(\overline{A})} = \mathcal{E}$. Conversely assume that $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$. Now $c_{\mu_I}^*(\overline{A}) = \overline{i_{\mu_I}^*(A)} = \mathcal{U}$. Therefore $A \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$. \square

Proposition 3.20. Let A be an ISs of X . Then $A \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$ iff $\overline{A} \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$.

Proposition 3.21. Let $A \subseteq X$. Then the following are true.

- (1) \mathcal{E} is always a μ_I g -CDGITS.
- (2) If $A \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$ then $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$.
- (3) If $A \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$ then $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$.
- (4) If $A \in Cd^*(\mu_I)$ then $b_{\mu_I}^*(A) = A$.

Definition 3.4. $A \subseteq X$ is said to be μ_I g -Somewhere Dense set in GITS (μ_I g -SDGITS) if there exist a non-void μ_I g -open set U such that $U \subseteq c_{\mu_I}^*(A)$. Equivalently $i_{\mu_I}^*(c_{\mu_I}^*(A)) \neq \mathcal{E}$. The collection of μ_I g -SDGITS is denoted as $Sd^*(\mu_I)$.

Example 3.8. In example:3.1, $Sd^*(\mu_I) = \{ \mathcal{O}, < X, \phi, \{1_X\} >, < X, \phi, \{2_X\} >, < X, \phi, \{3_X\} >, < X, \phi, \{1_X, 2_X\} >, < X, \phi, \{3_X, 1_X\} >, < X, \{1_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{1_X\}, \{2_X\} >, < X, \{1_X\}, \{2_X\} >, < X, \{2_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{2_X\}, \{1_X\} >, < X, \{2_X\}, \{3_X\} >, < X, \{2_X\}, \{1_X, 3_X\} >, < X, \{2_X, 3_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{3_X\}, \{1_X\} >, < X, \{3_X\}, \{2_X\} >, < X, \{3_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{3_X\}, \{1_X, 2_X\} >, < X, \{2_X, 3_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{2_X, 1_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{2_X, 3_X\}, \{1_X\} >, < X, \{1_X, 3_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{1_X, 3_X\}, \{2_X\} >, < X, \{2_X, 1_X\}, \{3_X\} >, \mathcal{U} \}$.

Remark 3.6. The complement of a μ_I g -SDGITS need not be a μ_I g -SDGITS. From the above example the complement of $< X, \{2_X, 3_X\}, \phi >$ is $< X, \phi, \{3_X, 2_X\} >$ which is not a μ_I g -SDGITS.

Proposition 3.22. Let $A \subseteq X$. Then the following are true.

- (i) \mathcal{E} is not a μ_I g -SDGITS.
- (ii) \mathcal{U} is a μ_I g -SDGITS.
- (iii) If $A \in Sd^*(\mu_I)$ then $c_{\mu_I}^*(A) \in Sd^*(\mu_I)$.
- (iv) Every superset of a μ_I g -SDGITS is a μ_I g -SDGITS.

4. μ_I g -Baire spaces in GITS

In this part, we present a μ_I g -Baire space using μ_I g -NDGITS. Also we speak about some results using μ_I g -Baire space.

Definition 4.1. An ISS A of X is called $\mu_I g$ -meager or $\mu_I g$ -first category ($\mu_I g$ -FCGITS) if $A = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} B_i$, where B_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS. The collection of $\mu_I g$ -FCGITS represents as $\mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$. Remaining sets are called $\mu_I g$ -second category ($\mu_I g$ -SCGITS). The complement of $\mu_I g$ -FCGITS is called a $\mu_I g$ -residual set.

Example 4.1. Consider the topological space $X = \{i_X, j_X, k_X\}$ with $\mu_I = \{\mathcal{E}, < X, \phi, \{j_X\}\rangle, < X, \{i_X\}, \phi\rangle, < X, \{i_X, j_X\}, \phi\rangle, < X, \{i_X\}, \{k_X\}\rangle\}$. Then $Nd^*(\mu_I) = \{< X, \phi, \{i_X, j_X\}\rangle, \mathcal{E}, < X, \{k_X\}, \{i_X, j_X\}\rangle\}$. The union of $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS is $\{< X, \{k_X\}, \{i_X, j_X\}\rangle\}$ which is named as a $\mu_I g$ -FCGITS and $< X, \{i_X, j_X\}, \{k_X\}\rangle$ is called a $\mu_I g$ -residual set.

Proposition 4.1. Let $A \subseteq X$. If $A \in \mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$ then $\bar{A} = \cap_{i=1}^{\infty} B_i$ where B_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -DGITS.

Proof. Let $A \in \mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$. Then $A = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i$, where A_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS. Now $\bar{A} = \overline{(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i)} = \cap_{i=1}^{\infty} (\bar{A}_i)$. Since A_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS, \bar{A}_i is a $\mu_I g$ -DGITS. Take $B_i = \bar{A}_i$. Therefore $\bar{A} = \cap_{i=1}^{\infty} B_i$ where B_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -DGITS. \square

Proposition 4.2. Every subset of a $\mu_I g$ -FCGITS set is $\mu_I g$ -FCGITS.

Proof. Let A be a $\mu_I g$ -FCGITS. Then $A = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} N_i$, where N_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS. Suppose $A \subseteq B = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} N_i$. Therefore $A \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} N_i$ which implies $A \subseteq N_i$, for some $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS. By using proposition : 3.15 (i), A is a $\mu_I g$ -FCGITS. \square

Definition 4.2. If $i_{\mu_I}^*(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i) = \mathcal{E}$, where A_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS then X is a $\mu_I g$ -Baire space. In example : 4.1, $i_{\mu_I}^*(< X, \{k_X\}, \{i_X, j_X\}\rangle) = \mathcal{E}$. Hence (X, μ_I) is a $\mu_I g$ -Baire space.

Proposition 4.3. If $i_{\mu_I}^*(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i) = \mathcal{E}$, where $i_{\mu_I}^*(A_i) = \mathcal{E}$ and A_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -open sets in X , then (X, μ_I) is a $\mu_I g$ -Baire space.

Proof. Given that A_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -open sets in X and $i_{\mu_I}^*(A_i) = \mathcal{E}$. By Corollary:3.2, A_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS. Therefore $i_{\mu_I}^*(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i) = \mathcal{E}$, A_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS and hence (X, μ_I) is a $\mu_I g$ -Baire space. \square

Proposition 4.4. If $c_{\mu_I}^*(\cap_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i) = \mathcal{U}$, where A_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -open and $\mu_I g$ -DGITS, then (X, μ_I) is a $\mu_I g$ -Baire space.

Proof. Given that $c_{\mu_I}^*(\cap_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i) = \mathcal{U}$ which gives $\overline{(c_{\mu_I}^*(\cap_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i))} = \mathcal{E} \Rightarrow i_{\mu_I}^*(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} (\bar{A}_i)) = \mathcal{E}$. Take $B_i = \bar{A}_i$. Then $i_{\mu_I}^*(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} B_i) = \mathcal{E}$. Now $A_i \in \mu_I g$ -open implies that \bar{A}_i is a $\mu_I g$ -closed set in (X, μ_I) and hence B_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -closed and $i_{\mu_I}^*(B_i) = i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}_i) = c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}_i) = \mathcal{E}$. By corollary : 3.2 B_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS. Hence $i_{\mu_I}^*(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} B_i) = \mathcal{E}$ where B_i 's are $\mu_I g$ -NDGITS which implies that (X, μ_I) is a $\mu_I g$ -Baire space. \square

Proposition 4.5. Let (X, μ_I) be a GITS. Then the following are equivalent

- (i) (X, μ_I) is a $\mu_I g$ -Baire space.
- (ii) $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$, for every $A \in \mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$.

(iii) $c_{\mu_I}^*(B) = \mathcal{U}$, for every μ_I g -residual set B in X .

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii), Let $A \in \mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$. Then $A = (\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i)$ where A_i 's are μ_I g -NDGITS. Now $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = i_{\mu_I}^*(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i) = \mathcal{E}$, which gives $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Let B be a μ_I g -residual set in (X, μ_I) . Then $\bar{B} \in \mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$ in X . From (ii), $i_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{B}) = \mathcal{E} \Rightarrow \overline{(c_{\mu_I}^*(B))} = \mathcal{E}$. Hence $c_{\mu_I}^*(B) = \mathcal{U}$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) Let $A \in \mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$. Then $A = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i$ where A_i 's are μ_I g -NDGITS. We have, if $A \in \mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$ in X then \bar{A} is a μ_I g -residual set. By (iii) we get $c_{\mu_I}^*(\bar{A}) = \mathcal{U}$, which gives $\overline{(i_{\mu_I}^*(A))} = \mathcal{U}$. Therefore $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = \mathcal{E}$ and hence $i_{\mu_I}^*(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i) = \mathcal{E}$, where A_i 's are μ_I g -NDGITS. Hence (X, μ_I) is a μ_I g -Baire space. \square

Proposition 4.6. *Every μ_I g -FCGITS is a μ_I g -rare set.*

Proof. Let $A \in \mathcal{F}^*(\mu_I)$. By the definition:4.1, we have $A = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i$, where A_i 's are μ_I g -NDGITS. Now $i_{\mu_I}^*(A) = i_{\mu_I}^*(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i) = \mathcal{E}$, since (X, μ_I) is a μ_I g -Baire space. Hence A is a μ_I g -rare set. \square

Remark 4.1. *The converse of Proposition:4.6 is not valid. Now we elaborate with the help of succeeding illustration.*

Illustration 4.1. *Consider the topological space $X = \{e_X, s_X, t_X\}$ with $\mu_I = \{\mathcal{E}, \{< X, \{s_X\}, \phi >, < X, \{e_X\}, \{s_X\} >, < X, \{e_X, s_X\}, \phi >\}$. Then μ_I g -rare set = $\{< X, \phi, \{e_X, s_X\} >, \mathcal{E}, < X, \{t_X\}, \{e_X, s_X\} >\}$ but $< X, \phi, \{e_X, s_X\} >$ and \mathcal{E} are not a μ_I g -FCGITS.*

5. Conclusion

In this paper, the relation between μ_I g -DGITS and μ_I g -Exterior are to be contemplated and also the correlations between μ_I g -NDGITS, μ_I g -CDGITS, μ_I g -rare sets and μ_I g -Border of a GITS (X, μ_I) were discussed.

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